

THERMAL ANALYSIS AND MICROSTRUCTURE OF FURFURAL ACETONE RESIN-DERIVED CARBON

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1 Introduction

Furfural acetone (FA) resin is a kind of furan resins which refer to a family of thermosetting resins containing furan ring in the molecular structure, and the FA resin was applied in many fields such as precursor for C/C composites and glass-like carbon (GC) materials due to its excellent corrosion resistance and high carbon yield [1]. And the commonly used precursors for C/C or GC are acetone-furfural, phenol-formaldehyde and polyfurfuryl alcohol, pyrolyzed in the inert or in a vacuum atmosphere in order to avoid oxidation [1-7]. The pyrolysis process of FA precursor is very important, it converts the FA to amorphous carbon, so the pyrolysis mechanism and the change of structure are deserved to investigate. The commonly utilized methods are thermogravimetric analysis (TGA), X-ray diffraction (XRD), Raman spectroscopy and scanning electron microscopy (SEM) [1-7]. L. Xia [1] has studied the GC made from acetone-furfural/phosphorous acid system by XRD, SEM which was carbonized at 850 °C in nitrogen atmosphere followed by heat treatment in the range of 1200-2500 °C in inert atmosphere. A. Sharma [2] has compared the structure parameters of phenol formaldehyde resin char by XRD and TEM techniques. H. Zhou [3] has studied the microstructure and performance of FA/industry phosphorous derived carbon and its matrix C/C composites. H. Qiu [4] has investigated the structure conversion of polyfurfuryl alcohol and polyfurfuryl ketone derived carbon by XRD. K. Nakamura [5] has studied the surface oxidation behavior at 500 °C of GC derived from furfuryl alcohol/*p*-toluenesulfonic acid by thermogravimetric analysis (TGA), Raman spectroscopy and X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS). J. Tu [6] has studied the GC derived from phenol-formaldehyde by laser Raman micro-spectroscopy. T. Ko [7] has reported the pore structure of GC derived from resole-type phenol-formaldehyde by transmission electron microscopy (TEM) and electron diffraction (ED). However, the relevant report on benzene

sulphonyl chloride (BSC) as curing agent is few in open literature. The motivation of the present work is to acquire a better understanding of this system. In the present study, four techniques were used to give insight to the physical and chemical properties of FA/BSC system.

2 Experimental

2.1 Materials

FA resin and the curing agent benzene sulphonyl chloride (BSC) was provided by the plant of research center for composite materials, and the weight ratio of FA to BSC is 100:1, 100:1.5, 100:2, designated as 1#, 2#, 3#. The mixture was dispersed by ultrasonic for 1 h to yield a homogeneous mixture. The mixture was held in a plastic pot and was cured stepwise at 30 °C for 700 h, then at 50 °C for 24 h, and at 60 °C for 84 h in the end in an oven. The carbonization process is as follows: 25~160 °C/0.5 h, 160 °C/2 h, 160~400 °C/24 h, 400~500 °C/5 h, 500~700 °C/5 h, 700~800 °C/1 h, 800~950 °C/1 h, 950 °C/2 h in vacuum. After carbonization, the samples 1#, 2#, 3# were named as C1#, C2#, C3#, respectively.

2.2 TGA measurement

The thermogravimetric analyzer was utilized to investigate the TGA. The system 1# was heated at four heating rates (5, 7.5, 10 and 15 °C·min⁻¹), and the systems 2# and 3# were heated at 10 °C·min⁻¹ from 30 °C to 800 °C under nitrogen atmosphere.

2.3 XRD measurement

The X-ray diffraction (XRD) was measured for a bulk sample on X-ray diffractometer (D/MAX) using Cu *K* α -radiation ($\lambda=0.154$ nm). The X-ray intensity was measured in the range of $10^\circ \leq 2\theta \leq 90^\circ$ with a scan speed of 0.02°/sec.

2.4 Raman spectroscopy measurement

The measurements were carried out with a Renishaw Raman spectrometer from the samples using an

argon ion laser, the wavelength of laser is 514.5 nm. The samples were scanned between 1000 and 2000 cm^{-1} .

2.5 SEM measurement

The six samples were coated with gold prior to the SEM observation, and the equipment is JSM-6700F.

3 Results and Discussion

3.1 Pyrolysis kinetic analysis

For TG experiments the kinetic analysis was carried out by using the conversion a , which can be described by the following expression [8, 9]:

$$a = \frac{m_i - m_t}{m_i - m_f} \quad (1)$$

Where m_i is the initial sample mass, m_t is the mass at time t and m_f is the final mass.

Generally, the pyrolysis reaction rate can be assumed as follow:

$$\frac{da}{dt} = A \exp\left(-\frac{E_a}{RT}\right) f(a) \quad (2)$$

Where A is the Arrhenius pre-exponential factor, E_a is the apparent activation energy, R is the universal gas constant, T is the absolute temperature and $f(a)$ is the kinetic mechanism function of the thermal pyrolysis process tabulated in Table 1 [10].

In order to confirm the appropriate pyrolysis reaction model, the apparent activation energy E_a is prerequisite, and E_a is usually obtained by Ozawa method described by the equation below:

$$E_a = -\frac{R}{1.052} \frac{d \ln \beta}{d(1/T_p)} \quad (3)$$

Where β is the heating rate and T_p is the peak temperature from the curve of conversion rate versus temperature.

After the determination of the apparent activation energy, the function of the pyrolysis process is needed to get the kinetic model. For this purpose, one special function, H , is constructed to determine the appropriate function $f(a)$. The function H is expressed as follows:

$$H = \frac{da}{dt} \exp\left(\frac{E_a}{RT}\right) = Af(a) \quad (4)$$

Taking natural logarithms of Eq. (4), Eq. (5) is generated.

$$\ln H = \ln A + \ln f(a) \quad (5)$$

The Arrhenius pre-exponential factor A can be calculated from the intercept of the plot of $\ln H$ versus $\ln f(a)$.

The above analysis is based on the assumption of the same apparent activation energy all over the pyrolysis process, but in fact the pyrolysis process is very complex and the apparent activation energy changed during the process, so the model-free iso-conversional methods are employed to analyze the apparent activation energy at a given isoconversional conversion. The isoconversional differential method is expressed by Eq. (6) [11], and the isoconversional integral method proposed by Flynn-Wall-Ozawa is based on Eq. (7) [12].

$$\left[\frac{\partial \ln(da/dt)}{\partial T^{-1}} \right]_a = -\frac{E_{a1}}{R} \quad (6)$$

$$\ln \beta = \text{const} - \frac{1.05E_{a2}}{RT_a} \quad (7)$$

Where the subscript a represents the specific conversion, and E_a and T_a are the effective activation energy and temperature for the specific conversion, respectively.

The profiles of weight residual versus temperature for 1#, 2# and 3# pyrolyzed in N_2 at the rate of $10^\circ\text{C}/\text{min}$ are presented in Fig. 1. As can be seen from Fig. 1 that the decomposition temperature for 1# was higher than that of the other two systems, and the curves for 2# and 3# were nearly superposition. The char yield for 1#, 2# and 3# at 795°C are 57.54%, 51.64% and 51.11%, respectively. The char yield for 1# was higher than that of the other two systems which was ascribed to the tight structure for 1#, so the optimum ratio of FA to BSC was 100:1 for the system.

The derivative thermogravimetric analysis (DTG) for 1#, 2# and 3# at the rate of $10^\circ\text{C}/\text{min}$ as a function of temperature is illustrated in Fig. 2. It was noted that there were two-stage pyrolysis process for 2# and 3#, however, one-stage pyrolysis process for 1#, which was due to the shorter chain length for 1#. The main reaction during pyrolysis was thermal condensations, by-products such as gas water, methane, carbon dioxide and carbon monoxide were produced after the rupture of methyl and the furan ring open. At the end of the pyrolysis the six-membered aromatic ring generated and dehydrogenation took place, which led to the production of graphite structure [1, 13].

The profiles of weight residual versus temperature for 1# pyrolyzed in N_2 at various heating rate are presented in Fig. 3. As noted that the curves were

shifted to higher temperatures with the increasing heating rates. The conversion versus temperature for 1# at various heating rate is shown in Fig. 4 and the curves were shifted to higher temperatures with the heating rate increment as well. The conversion rate as a function of time and temperature at different heating rates are presented in Fig. 5 and Fig. 6, respectively. The higher the heating rates, the shorter time to reach the maximum of the conversion rate and the higher temperature to reach the maximum of the conversion rate.

According to Eq. (3), E_a can be calculated from the slope of linear plot of $\ln \beta$ versus $1/T_p$, the calculated E_a was found to be 128.87 kJ/mol. But the pyrolysis is a complicated process, so a simple apparent activation energy used to express the complex process was not accurate. The model-free isoconversional kinetic analysis can provide more detail pyrolysis mechanism.

The correlation between E_a and conversion was an indication of the change of pyrolysis process. The plots of the isoconversional analysis according to Eq. (7) at given conversion are illustrated in Fig. 7. The calculated E_a and the correlation coefficient are listed in Table 2. As can be seen that the E_{a2} was increasing with conversion increment, but the change tendency of E_{a2} was fluctuated in the range of conversion from 0.3 to 0.7.

After E_a calculated, we can obtain the function H , which is shown in Fig. 8. Compared the shapes between H and $f(a)$, the most probable mechanism was the diffusion model. Substituting the diffusion models into Eq. (5), the fitting results are summarized in Table 3. The correlation coefficient of D3 was higher than that of the other two symbols, and the mean value of $\ln A$ was 14.79.

Therefore, pyrolysis kinetic model can be expressed as follows:

$$\frac{da}{dt} = 2.65 \times 10^6 \exp\left(-\frac{15500}{T}\right) \frac{3(1-a)^{2/3}}{2[1-(1-a)^{1/3}]} \quad (8)$$

3.2 X-ray Diffraction analysis

XRD is a widely used method to investigate the microstructure of carbonaceous materials [2, 14-17]. XRD patterns of the six samples before and after carbonization are illustrated in Fig. 9 and Fig. 10, respectively. As can be seen that in Fig. 9 there was one peak in each curve *ca.* 21°, and the peaks were shifted to lower angle with the increasing of curing agent content, which was the indication of regular structure of cure product. In Fig. 10, it was noted

that there were three peaks for each curve in the range of 10° to 90°, they were *ca.* 22°, 43°, 79° respectively, which were corresponding to the planes (002), (100) and (110). These bands are used to get the crystallite size. The structure parameters can be calculated by the Bragg equation and Scherrer equation [18]. The equations are as follows:

Bragg equation:

$$n\lambda = 2d \sin \theta \quad (9)$$

Scherer equation:

$$L = \frac{K\lambda}{\beta \cos \theta} \quad (10)$$

Where n is the diffraction series, λ is the wavelength of X-ray (0.154 nm), d is the interlayer spacing, θ is Bragg angle or half diffraction angle, K is a constant which is 0.9 for L_c calculation and 1.84 for L_a calculation, β is the full width at half maxima, L_c is the mean size of crystal in the c -direction obtained from (002) band and L_a is the mean size of crystal in the a -direction from (100) band.

The structure parameters are summarized in Table 4. It was observed that L_c was in the range of 0.3~0.5 nm, L_a was in the range of 2~6 nm, which was indicative of the disordered layer structure. It was corresponding to the results reported in the open literatures.

3.3 Raman spectroscopy

Raman spectroscopy is an effective nondestructive tool to characterize the structures of carbons [19-22]. There are two strong characteristic bands for graphite-like structures of carbons, which are corresponding to 1580 and 1360 cm^{-1} respectively. The former one is usually called as graphitic (G-band) and the latter one is existed not in crystalline graphite but in the disordered carbons, called D-band. G-band is due to the in-plane zone center phonons of E_{2g} symmetry and the D-band is assigned to K -point phonons of A_{1g} symmetry. The two vibration modes are shown in Fig. 11 [6].

Raman spectra of samples after carbonization are presented in Fig. 12. The peaks are listed in Table 5, it was observed that the D-bands were close to each other, and G-bands were near at different FA to BSC ratios as well. D-band and G-band were not just happened to 1360 and 1580 cm^{-1} respectively. Lorenz function was utilized to analyze the structures of glassy carbon. Fig. 13 presents the curve fits for the Raman spectra of sample 1#. The integral area was referred as relative intensity, Tuinstra and Koenig related the relative intensity of

the D and G bands to the graphitic crystallite structure, which is expressed as follows [23]:

$$R = \frac{I_D}{I_G} = \frac{C(\lambda)}{L_a} \quad (11)$$

Where $C(\lambda)$ is a parameter related to laser wavelength, 4.4 nm when the wavelength is 0.154 nm, and L_a is the size of the crystallite, I_D and I_G are the integral intensity for D-band and G-band, respectively. The fitting results are tabulated in Table 5. From Table 5 it can be seen that ratio R and L_a were near the same, respectively, which indicates that the FA to BSC ration did not influence the structure in the a -direction of glassy carbon. Meanwhile, L_a was near to the value calculated by XRD.

3.4 SEM analysis

The SEM photographs of the fracture surface of carbon derived from FA/BSC are shown in Fig. 14. From C1# in Fig. 14 we can see that the fracture surface was smooth like glass rupture surface and some pores and cracks existed; and from C2# in Fig. 14 it was noted that there were so many needle-like particles on the surface and also some pores existed; and from C3# in Fig. 14 it was observed that the particles were granular, not needle-like. And the pores were observed between the interfaces of the particles, meanwhile, the bigger pores were filled with smaller particles.

When the precursor was decomposed, the structure was damaged, and the pyrolysis products were evolved in gas state such as CO_2 , CO , CH_2 , and H_2O . But due to the high carbon content, the residual component was mainly carbon atoms with high activity, and migrated to form a stable structure, so the pores emerged. During the migration, the pores may be coarsened caused by two mechanisms [24, 25]. One is the combining of small pores, the other one is due to the swelling induced by expansion of pyrolysis gases. In brief, the ordering of local carbon structure gave rise to the pore coarsening.

4 Conclusions

In the present study, FA/BSC system was investigated by four techniques. When the ratio of FA to BSC was 100:1, the decomposition temperature was higher than that of other samples and the char yield was the highest. The pyrolysis reaction mechanism was three-dimensional diffusion. XRD was used to investigate the structure parameters of the samples at different FA/BSC ratio before and after carbonization and the results were

not changed greatly from each other. Raman spectroscopy was also used to characterize the structures of glass-like carbon and the size of crystallite was obtained. From the SEM photographs the smooth fracture surface was exhibited and needle-like and granular particles were observed, the pores were existed as well due to the mobility of atoms.

Table 1 The most widely used kinetic models $f(a)$

Mechanism	Symbol	$f(a)$
Phase boundary controlled reaction(contracting area)	R2	$(1-a)^{1/2}$
Phase boundary controlled reaction(contracting volume)	R3	$(1-a)^{2/3}$
Random nucleation followed by an instantaneous growth of nuclei	F1	$(1-a)$
Random nucleation and growth of nuclei through different nucleation and nucleus growth models	An	$n(1-a)[- \ln(1-a)]^{1-1/n}$
2-D diffusion	D2	$1/[- \ln(1-a)]$
3-D diffusion (Jander equation)	D3	$3(1-a)^{2/3}/2[1-(1-a)^{1/3}]$
3-D diffusion (Ginstling-Brounshein equation)	D4	$3/2[(1-a)^{-1/3}-1]$

Fig. 1 The weight residual versus temperature for 1#, 2# and 3# at the rate of 10 °C/min

Fig. 2 The derivative weight residual versus temperature for 1#, 2# and 3# at the rate of 10 °C/min

Fig. 5 The rate of conversion as a function of time at different heating rates for sample 1#

Fig. 3 The weight residual versus temperature for 1# at various heating rate

Fig. 6 The rate of conversion as a function of temperature at different heating rates for sample 1#

Fig. 4 The conversion versus temperature for 1# at various heating rate

Fig. 7 The fitting results at different conversion for sample 1#

Table 2 Activation energy values for different values of conversion and the correlation coefficients

a	$E_{a1}(\text{kJ/mol})$	R^2	$E_{a2}(\text{kJ/mol})$	R^2
0.1	62.17	0.9799	74.92	0.9709
0.2	135.77	0.9887	114.66	0.9846
0.3	246.58	0.9421	153	0.988
0.4	189.47	0.9949	189.35	0.9793
0.5	203.81	0.9933	195.03	0.9914
0.6	183.79	0.9941	206.27	0.9953
0.7	203.26	0.9811	223.69	0.9977
0.8	301.7	0.9893	258.4	0.9994
0.9	278.02	0.9978	341.5	0.9978

Fig. 8 Function H versus conversion a

Table 3 Fitting results for symbols at different heating rates

Symbol	5 °C/min		7.5 °C/min		15 °C/min	
	$\ln A$	R^2	$\ln A$	R^2	$\ln A$	R^2
D2	18.82	0.935	17.39	0.989	17.79	0.978
D3	14.18	0.98	14.76	0.992	15.44	0.982
D4	13.44	0.979	14.15	0.99	14.88	0.98

Fig. 9 XRD patterns before carbonization

Fig. 10 XRD patterns after carbonization

Table 4 XRD analysis results for the samples

sample	d_{002}/nm	L_c/nm	d_{100}/nm	L_a/nm	d_{110}/nm
1#	0.42	0.351			
2#	0.427	0.385			
3#	0.442	0.932			
C1#	0.395	0.644	0.21	2.28	0.1206
C2#	0.398	0.638	0.207	2.259	0.122
C3#	0.372	0.685	0.21	2.344	0.121

Fig. 11 E_{2g} and A_{1g} vibrational modes corresponding to 1580 cm^{-1} and 1360 cm^{-1} of Raman spectra

Fig. 12 Raman spectra of samples after carbonization

Fig. 13 Curve fits for the Raman spectra of sample 1#

Table 5 Raman spectroscopic parameters obtained after curve fitting and the microcrystalline size

Sam ple	Raman shift/ cm^{-1}		FWHM/ cm^{-1}		R	L_a/nm
	D- band	G- band	D- band	G- band		
1%	1356	1594	192.2	83.5	2.03	2.16
1.5%	1354	1593	197.1	83.4	2.08	2.12
2%	1354	1592	202.5	87.5	2.04	2.16

Fig. 14 SEM photographs of carbon derived from FA/BSC

References

- [1] L. Xia, H. Zhang and X. Xiong "Pyrolysis of furfural-acetone resin as matrix precursor for new carbon materials". *Journal of Central South University Technology*, 15, 753-756, 2008.
- [2] A. Sharma, T. Kyotani and A. Tomita "Comparison of structural parameters of PF carbon from XRD and HRTEM techniques". *Carbon*, 38, 1977-1984, 2000.
- [3] H. Zhou, X. Zhang and W. Zou "Study on microstructure and performance of FA resin carbon and FA resin matrix carbon-carbon composites". *Journal of Solid Rocket Technology*, 30, 3, 260-263, 2007.
- [4] H. Qiu and G. Zhao "Study on the structural conversions during the preparation of glassy carbon from furan resin using XRD". *New Carbon Materials*, 14, 2, 49-53, 1999.
- [5] K. Nakamura, Y. Tanabe and M. Fukushima "Analysis of surface oxidation behavior at 500 °C under dry air of glass-like carbon heat-treated from 1200 to 3000 °C". *Materials Science and Engineering B*, 161, 40-45, 2009.
- [6] J. Tu, L. Zhang and J. Peng "Study on the glass-like carbon derived from phenolic resin by laser Raman micro-spectroscopy". *Polymer Materials Science and Engineering*, 21, 6, 205-208, 2005.
- [7] T. Ko, H. Hu and J. Ting "The pore structure of a glass-like carbon as revealed by transmission electron microscopy". *New Carbon Materials*, 20, 4, 365-368, 2005.
- [8] J. Wang, L. Guo and H. Li "Curing characteristics and kinetic analysis of furfural acetone resin used as carbon/carbon composites precursor". *Journal of Solid Rocket Technology*, 35, 1, 123-126, 2012.
- [9] H. Jiang, J. Wang and S. Wu "Pyrolysis kinetics of phenol-formaldehyde resin by non-isothermal thermogravimetry". *Carbon*, 48, 352-358, 2010.
- [10] P. Sanchez-Jimenez, L. Perez-Maqueda and A. Perejon "Combined kinetic analysis of thermal degradation of polymeric materials under any thermal pathway". *Polymer Degradation and Stability*, 94, 2079-2085, 2009.
- [11] S. Vyazovkin, A. Burnham and J. Criado "ICTAC kinetics committee recommendations for performing kinetic computations on thermal analysis data". *Thermochimica Acta*, 520, 1-19, 2011.
- [12] S. Vyazovkin "Model-free kinetics staying free of multiplying entities without necessity". *Journal Thermal Analysis Calorimetry*, 83, 45-51, 2006.
- [13] L. Xia, H. Zhang and X. Xiong "Curing reaction of furfural acetone resin used for new carbon materials". *The Chinese Journal of Nonferrous Metals*, 18, 6, 953-958, 2008.
- [14] L. Xia, H. Zhang and X. Xiong "Effects of heat treatment temperature on oxidation behavior of glass-like carbon derived from acetone-furfural resin". *Transaction of Nonferrous Metals Society of China*, 21, 330-334, 2011.
- [15] X. Wang, G. Zhang and Y. Zhang "Graphitization of glassy carbon prepared under high temperature and high pressures". *Carbon*, 41, 179-198, 2003.
- [16] X. Ding, Y. Zhuang and J. Wang "Studies on the pyrolytic product of high char polyarylacetylene". *Thermosetting Resin*, 19, 2, 5-8, 2004.
- [17] Y. Korai, K. Sakamoto and I. Moshida "Structural correlation between micro-texture of furan resin and its derived glass-like carbon". *Carbon*, 42, 219-238, 2004.
- [18] H. Honda, S. Toyoda and K. Kobayashi "Vitro carbon made from acetone-furfural resin: X-ray diffraction and ESR of vitro carbon". *TANSO*, 47, 8-14, 1966.
- [19] G. Li, Z. Lu and B. Huang "Raman scattering investigation of carbons obtained by heat treatment of a polyfurfuryl alcohol". *Solid State Ionics*, 89, 327-331, 1996.
- [20] Y. Tanabe, K. Hoshi and M. Ishibashi "Effect of the size and the amount of surface functional groups of inclusions on microstructure development in Furan resin-derived carbon". *Carbon*, 39, 287-324, 2001.
- [21] Y. Wang, D. Alsmeyer and R. McCreery "Raman spectroscopy of carbon materials: structure basis of observed spectra". *Chemical Materials*, 2, 557-563, 1990.
- [22] R. Escribano, J. Sloan and N. Siddique "Raman spectroscopy of carbon-containing particles". *Vibrational Spectroscopy*, 26, 179-186, 2001.
- [23] L. Pesin "Review: Structure and properties of glass-like carbon". *Journal of Materials Science*, 37, 1-28, 2002.
- [24] S. Bose, R. Bragg "Kinetics of pore coarsening in glassy carbon". *Carbon*, 19, 4, 289-295, 1981.
- [25] J. Wang, Z. Guan "Structure analysis during manufacturing process of glassy carbon". *Journal of Northeast Normal University*, 3, 63-66, 1995.